

Work-Related Stressors of Elementary School Teachers

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Abstract:

Teaching is widely recognized as a highly stressful profession. This study assessed the degree of work-related stressors among elementary school teachers in a medium-sized division in Southern Negros Island, Central Philippines, during the 2022–2023 school year to inform a psycho-social wellness plan. Data were gathered from 285 respondents through a validated and reliable self-made instrument. Most respondents were young, had lower educational attainment, and held lower plantilla positions. Findings revealed that teachers experienced a high degree of stress in terms of job demands, but only a low degree in interpersonal relationships and job roles. Regardless of age, educational attainment, or plantilla position, respondents consistently reported high stress in job demands and low stress in the other two areas. Statistical analysis confirmed no significant differences in stress levels based on demographic groupings, suggesting uniform perceptions of stress across all categories. Heavy workloads were a common stressor, while issues with colleagues or role clarity were less prominent.

Keywords: Elementary school teachers, work-related stressors, interpersonal relationships, job demands, job role

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Teaching is widely recognized as one of the most stressful professions globally, with teachers reporting high levels of work-related stress that significantly impact their job performance (Agai-Demjaha et al., 2017; Cox et al., 2018). Studies across various countries, including those in Europe, Canada, and Africa, have consistently shown alarming levels of stress among educators. For instance, extreme stress affects 10–40% of teachers in Europe, while nearly 75% of Canadian teachers report stress, and similar trends are seen in Egypt, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. In the Philippines, the situation is equally concerning, with rising cases of teacher burnout and mental health issues, although specific suicide statistics remain limited. A 2021 survey by the Alliance of Concerned Teachers revealed that over 70% of Filipino teachers felt their physical and mental health suffered due to the demands of distance learning, with 10% reporting illness caused by the strain. Extended work hours, lack of sufficient leave benefits, and overwhelming workloads continue to exacerbate these challenges in the teaching profession.

The continuous changes in the educational system have significantly contributed to increased stress levels among teachers, primarily due to new responsibilities, shifting roles, and heightened expectations from superiors (Eres & Atanasovska, 2017). These changes are driven by evolving demands in technology, quality assurance, standardization, and cost efficiency, placing immense pressure on educators to meet the expectations of various stakeholders (Greenberg et al., 2018). In the Philippines, the full implementation of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act 10533), which extended basic education to 12 years, further transformed teachers' roles and workloads (Romero & Bantigue, 2017). Teachers are now expected to juggle numerous tasks, including managing heavier paperwork, addressing the behavioral needs of a diverse student population, and participating in frequent seminars, trainings, and reporting duties. These compounded responsibilities have led to psychological challenges such as stress, dissatisfaction, disengagement, and, in extreme cases, depression, anxiety, and even suicide.

In District II of Himamaylan City, the researcher observed that the COVID-19 pandemic forced teachers into unpredictable circumstances, accelerating the shift from traditional to online learning and disrupting social interactions, which impacted their mental health. This study aims to explore how teachers have adapted to the new educational system, particularly in managing increased workloads and reporting responsibilities, while maintaining effective teaching through distance learning modalities. Recognizing the mental and psychological strain brought about by these changes, the research underscores the importance of safeguarding teachers' well-being to sustain their motivation and sense of social responsibility. Motivated by firsthand experience as a School Head, the researcher seeks to assess the level of work-related stressors among elementary school teachers in a medium-sized division in Southern Negros Island. While burnout and stress among Filipino teachers have been acknowledged, there is limited

research on their broader mental health effects. This study aims to address that gap and contribute to the development of a psychosocial wellness plan that promotes teachers' overall health and well-being.

Current State of Knowledge

Work-related stress among teachers has become a significant concern due to its impact on job performance, well-being, and institutional outcomes. Frameworks such as the Person-Environment Fit Model (Vleugels et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2020) and the updated Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory (Demerouti & Bakker, 2023) show how mismatches between personal attributes and workplace conditions—exacerbated by crises like COVID-19—heighten stress, with job demands like workload and time pressure leading to burnout, while resources such as autonomy and social support enhance motivation. Hazardous working conditions, administrative overload, and poor relationships are prevalent stressors in the teaching profession (Alson, 2019). Coping strategies, such as emotion-focused and problem-focused approaches (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), are key in managing stress. Interventions based on JD-R and JDCS models (De Spiegelaere et al., 2020; CQ Net, 2023) emphasize autonomy, improved relationships, and balancing job demands with resources. In the Philippines, teacher suicides and mental health issues, linked to excessive workload and administrative tasks under the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, highlight the need for better stress management (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020). Chronic stress leads to absenteeism, disengagement, and burnout, particularly among teachers aged 31–50, emphasizing the need for supportive systems to address teacher stress and ensure educational success (Aftab & Kahtoon, 2012; Yahaya, 2010).

Multiple studies have confirmed that teaching is one of the most stressful professions, with factors such as work overload, large class sizes, lack of student motivation, and classroom discipline issues negatively impacting teacher performance (Clipa, 2017; Dankade, 2017). Haydon et al. (2018) also highlighted a range of stressors including role overload, unrealistic expectations, inadequate compensation, and poor working conditions. While stress often hampers performance, some studies in other sectors present contrasting findings: Vijayan (2018), Amoako et al. (2017), and Gharib et al. (2017) found that in certain contexts, work-related stress can positively influence performance, particularly when linked to workload or high demands. However, this is not universal—Hamid et al. (2017) and Awadh et al. (2017) emphasized that unresolved stress stemming from unfair promotion systems, poor job control, and lack of growth opportunities tends to reduce effectiveness, particularly in educational settings, reinforcing the urgent need for institutional support to manage stress and enhance employee well-being.

A range of studies highlights the multifaceted stressors experienced by Filipino teachers, particularly in public schools, where moderate to high levels of work-related stress impact teaching performance (Alson, 2019). Common stressors include hazardous working conditions, lack of resources, conflicting directives, time pressure, student misbehavior, and strict administrative monitoring, often leading to emotional burnout. Despite these, teachers maintain a high level of commitment to their profession, partly due to favorable factors like travel convenience in less urbanized areas. Orlanda-Ventayen et al. (2021) further emphasize that teachers are burdened with excessive workloads, often extending beyond school hours into their personal lives, as 75% of school hours are spent teaching while the rest is consumed by paperwork. The lack of recognition and the impact of autocratic leadership styles also diminish job satisfaction. Similarly, Rabago-Mingoa (2017) identifies the top stressors as paperwork, low salaries, high living costs, oversized classes, and being overly busy. These stressors persist across various teacher demographics. Outside the teaching profession, Mendoza (2019) notes that other careers, like veterinary work, are also prone to stress-related depression and suicidal ideation, linking heavy workloads and poor work-life balance as common occupational hazards.

Wellness is a broad, multidimensional concept defined as teachers' positive evaluation of their functioning in the work environment, encompassing outcomes like job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Collie et al., 2019). It involves a stress-free environment, which promotes physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual health, ultimately improving the quality of life and the ability to perform optimally, particularly in teaching (Reddy, 2017). Psychosocial wellbeing, which integrates psychological, social, and subjective components, influences overall functionality and helps individuals realize their potential as productive members of society (East African Community, 2019). Wellness, as a way of life, involves making healthy decisions and nurturing mind-body connections to cope with life's challenges (Travis, 2018). In an organizational context, a positive environment and supportive culture are essential for the success of wellness programs that reduce stress and improve overall health and performance (Royal et al., 2017; Kennedy, 2017). For teachers, wellbeing is linked to job satisfaction, work engagement, and teaching quality (Brouskeli et al., 2018; Viac et al., 2018).

Stress, an inevitable part of daily life, affects individuals both at home and in the workplace, impacting their health and balance. A stress-free environment promotes wellness, defined as the absence of illness or disease, which in turn improves the quality of life and community well-being (Ortillo, 2021). In academic institutions, wellness programs that support teachers in becoming physically fit, emotionally stable, and spiritually engaged are crucial for maintaining a healthy workforce. Stress in teaching, considered one of the most stressful occupations, can affect both personal and professional life, making wellness programs essential for teachers' holistic health. School principals play a key role in developing and implementing these programs, although challenges like resource allocation hinder

their success (Abanto, 2019). Research emphasizes the importance of wellness programs, with recommendations to improve teachers' mental health and quality of life (Sunga, 2019; Lope, 2019). Ortillo (2021) further highlights that a positive organizational environment significantly contributes to stress management and overall success.

Recent reports highlight significant concerns about teacher mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic in Canada. A survey by the Ottawa-Carleton District School Board (Pringle, 2020) revealed that teachers felt burnt out, exhausted, and overwhelmed by unsustainable workloads. Similarly, a survey by the Alberta Teachers' Association (ATA, 2020) showed that 95% of respondents reported stress, 94% reported fatigue, and 81% reported anxiety. Teachers across Canada are struggling to manage the increased complexity and pace of teaching during the pandemic, with many questioning their ability to continue despite their passion for education (Wong, 2020; Alhmidi, 2020). On a broader scale, studies like Moriyama et al. (2019) and Chen et al. (2019) have examined subjective well-being in different populations, finding that factors like social capital and resilience play critical roles in overall well-being, suggesting that fostering social connections and improving support systems can enhance well-being in challenging environments.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Recent updates to the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory emphasize its adaptability in crisis situations like the COVID-19 pandemic. By integrating crisis management literature, the extended model explains that employee well-being during turbulent times depends not only on job demands (such as heavy workloads, administrative tasks, and large class sizes) but also on job resources (such as autonomy, professional support, and professional learning opportunities). High job demands can lead to a depletion of energy and burnout, while sufficient job and personal resources can activate a motivational process, ultimately enhancing work engagement and overall well-being.

Building on this framework, recent research has begun exploring ways to support academic professionals and teacher's post-pandemic. Scholars argue for a more nuanced view that examines specific institutional, social, and psychological factors influencing well-being, rather than relying solely on broad categorizations of demands and resources. This comprehensive approach helps in understanding the links between these factors and outcomes like organizational commitment, job performance, and turnover intentions. In practical terms, applying the JD-R theory can inform interventions—such as psychosocial wellness programs and proactive measures to strengthen supervisory and colleague support—to help teachers better manage work-related stress while balancing responsibilities both at work and home.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers in the medium-sized division situated in Southern Negros Island, Central Philippines, during the School Year 2022 - 2023 as a basis for a Psychosocial Wellness Plan. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: 1) the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers according to the area of job demands, interpersonal relationships, and job role; 2) the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers when grouped according to the variables of age, highest educational attainment and Plantilla position; and 3) the significant difference in the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers when they are grouped and compared according to the variables.

Methodology:

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational design to examine the level of work-related stressors experienced by teachers and explore potential relationships with other variables. The design focuses on observing and analyzing existing conditions without manipulating variables, ensuring that findings reflect real-world data, which makes the proposed wellness program relevant. The aim is to describe how the selected demographic profile of elementary school teachers relates to their stress levels, serving as the basis for a psycho-social wellness program. Descriptive research, as defined by Creswell (2017), involves fact-finding and interpreting data about prevailing conditions, practices, and cause-effect relationships, and this study applies such methods to assess the current state and relationships between variables.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents comprised teachers from the 22 elementary schools under District 2, Division of Himamaylan City, during the School Year 2022 - 2023. Purposive sampling was used for this research to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis. Participants are chosen "on purpose," not randomly. It is also known as judgmental sampling or selective sampling.

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a modified version of The UCU Model Stress Questionnaire (Kinman & Siobhan/Wray, 2015) from the University and College Union (UCU) in the UK. It was divided into two parts: Part I collected demographic data on respondents' age, sex, highest educational attainment, and plantilla position, while Part II assessed the degree of work-related stressors in elementary school teachers across three areas: job demands, interpersonal relationships, and job role, with ten items per area (30 items in total). The survey was validated by a jury, and participants either completed it at their stations or via a Google link created by the researcher, with 30 minutes allotted for completion. It was subjected to validity (5.00-excellent) and reliability (0.973-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured a letter assuring the confidentiality of the respondents and the schools and asked permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Himamaylan City. When the permit was granted, the researcher attached the approved letter and furnished a copy to request the study's conduct. The researcher then reproduced the survey questionnaire according to the actual number of respondents in the study. The test was administered at a time most convenient for the respondents and conducted at their respective stations. It lasted approximately one hour and was followed by the distribution of the questionnaire. Filled-up questionnaires will be gathered, checked, and encoded. The scores will be treated accordingly and subjected to the SPSS software.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers according to the following areas: Job Demands, Interpersonal Relationships, and Job Role.

Objective No. 2, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine elementary school teachers' work-related stressors when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 3 used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether there is a significant difference in the degree of work-related stressors of elementary school teachers when they are grouped and compared according to the variables.

Ethical Consideration

The following are very important ethical considerations and were taken into account while carrying out this quantitative research: voluntary participation (respondents are not coerced into participating in the research), informed consent (respondents are completely informed of the different aspects of the research in comprehensible language), risk of harm (respondents are not placed in a situation where they are exposed to risk and harm for their willing participation), confidentiality (respondents are guaranteed that the information they have shared was not be disclosed to the public or to anyone for that matter), anonymity (respondents remain as anonymous in this research), among others (Andoh-Arthur, 2019).

Results and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Demands

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
A. Job Demands		
<i>As a teacher, I have</i>		
1. too many ancillary tasks.	4.09	High Degree
2. time pressured with deadlines like LIS, student profile, and parents' directory.	4.16	High Degree
3. overload teaching schedules	3.79	High Degree

4. difficulties in classroom management, like dealing with pupil's misbehavior	3.60	High Degree
5. hard time sustaining pupil's motivation in learning	3.49	Moderate Degree
6. insufficient time in making my Daily Lesson Plan, Daily Lesson Log, and Instructional Materials	3.89	High Degree
7. a big number of pupils to handle in my class	3.38	Moderate Degree
8. too many papers to be done for submission.	4.21	High Degree
9. too many things to do and not enough time to do it.	4.26	High Degree
10. To follow up on SF10, PSA Birth Certificate of students who transferred in.	3.48	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.84	High Degree

Table 1 shows the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job demands. The overall mean score is 3.84, interpreted as a "high degree."

Data further revealed that Item 5, "a big number of pupils to handle under my class," obtained the lowest mean of 3.38, interpreted as "moderate degree,". In contrast, Item 9, "too many things to do and not enough time to do it," got the highest mean of 4.26, interpreted as "high degree."

This implies that when teachers have a heavy workload, it can be difficult for them to find the time to complete all their tasks. This situation can lead to stress and potentially impact the quality of their work. Finding ways to manage their workload effectively, prioritize tasks, and possibly seek support or assistance can help alleviate some of the pressure. Additionally, advocating for resources and support from administrators or educational institutions can also be beneficial in ensuring that teachers can fulfill their responsibilities without being overwhelmed. This was supported to the study of (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020) that the requirements and expected outputs from their duties, obligations, responsibilities, and working condition as demanded by their work or school can cause a very stressful experience to the teacher respondents.

Table 2

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Interpersonal Relationships

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
B. Interpersonal Relationships		
<i>As a teacher,</i>		
1. I have to deal with personal harassment	2.22	Low Degree
2. I have to deal with conflicts with colleagues	2.29	Low Degree
3. I have to face hostile colleagues towards me	2.39	Low Degree
4. I have to accept feedback from colleagues	3.37	Moderate Degree
5. I am not appreciated for my work	2.40	Low Degree
6. I am not given technical assistance	2.35	Low Degree
7. I don't receive respect from my colleagues	1.77	Low Degree
8. I cannot establish harmonious relationships with my colleagues.	1.79	Low Degree
9. I solve problems on my own without getting help from my colleagues	2.71	Moderate Degree
10. I have difficulty getting feedback on my work-related issues.	2.33	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.36	Low Degree

Table 2 shows that the degree of work-related stressors in interpersonal relationships had an overall mean of 2.36, interpreted as a "low degree." Among the items, "I don't receive respect from my colleagues" scored the lowest mean of 1.77 ("low degree"), while "I have to accept feedback from colleagues" had the highest mean of 3.37 ("moderate degree"). This suggests that while feedback is vital for teachers' professional development, the stress from work overload may prevent them from adequately addressing it, impacting their growth and classroom effectiveness. Studies support the idea that positive teacher relationships can mitigate stress (Gebrekirstos, 2017; Gharib et al., 2017), with Filipino teachers' strong camaraderie and respect for colleagues potentially contributing to lower stress levels (Agai-Demjaha et al., 2017).

Table 3

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Roles

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Roles		

As a teacher,

1. I have many workloads.	3.62	High Degree
2. I have colleagues with conflicting ideas.	2.44	Low Degree
3. I have colleagues who overlap their job roles with mine.	2.14	Low Degree
4. I have unclear job descriptions.	2.12	Low Degree
5. I have poor interpersonal relationships	1.94	Low Degree
6. I lack proper orientation about my job	1.86	Low Degree
7. I have my limitations when it comes to my duties and responsibilities.	2.81	Moderate Degree
8. I cannot align my job rules with my future promotion.	2.18	Low Degree
9. I have broad (unclear) objectives and goals.	2.15	Low Degree
10. I have no direction in my career path.	1.87	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.31	Low Degree

Table 3 indicates that the degree of work-related stressors in the area of job roles had an overall mean of 2.31, interpreted as a "low degree." The item "I lack proper orientation about my job" had the lowest mean of 1.86 ("low degree"), while "I have many workloads" had the highest mean of 3.62 ("high degree"). This suggests that the selected public elementary school teachers were not stressed about their roles, although heavy workloads were a significant stressor. The Department of Education has acknowledged the issue and is working to reduce teacher workloads, including clerical tasks (Hernando-Malipot, 2018). Chronic work-related stress, caused by factors such as workload, students, and personal issues, can lead to absenteeism, disengagement, and high turnover (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020). Despite the challenges, stress can be managed positively to enhance performance, especially in teaching.

Table 4

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Demands According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I have</i>				
1. too many ancillary tasks.	4.18	High Degree	4.00	High Degree
2. time pressured with deadlines like LIS, student profile, and parents' directory.	4.20	High Degree	4.12	High Degree
3. overload teaching schedules	3.81	High Degree	3.76	High Degree
4. difficulties in classroom management, like dealing with pupil's misbehavior	3.50	High Degree	3.72	High Degree
5. hard time sustaining pupil's motivation to learn	3.43	Moderate Degree	3.55	High Degree
6. insufficient time in making my Daily Lesson Plan, Daily Lesson Log, and Instructional Materials	3.93	High Degree	3.85	High Degree
7. a significant number of pupils to handle in my class	3.26	Moderate Degree	3.52	High Degree
8. too many papers to be done for submission.	4.29	High Degree	4.12	High Degree
9. too many things to do and not enough time to do it.	4.35	High Degree	4.17	High Degree
10. to follow-up SF10, PSA Birth Certificate of students who transferred in.	3.52	High Degree	3.44	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.85	High Degree	3.82	High Degree

Table 4 presents the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job demands, categorized by age. Both the younger and older groups reported high levels of stress, with mean scores of 3.85 and 3.82, respectively. The younger group rated "a big number of pupils to handle under my class" with the lowest mean score of 3.26, interpreted as a "moderate degree," while the older group rated "to follow-up SF10, PSA Birth Certificate of students who transferred in" with a mean score of 3.44, also interpreted as a "moderate degree." However, both groups agreed that "too many things to do and not enough time to do it" was the highest stressor, with mean scores of 4.35 and 4.17, respectively, indicating a "high degree" of stress. These results align with Agai-Demjaha et al. (2017), who found that teachers over 45 years old tend to rate work-related stress as high, with a significant percentage reporting high stress levels.

Table 5

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Interpersonal Relationships According to Age

Categories		Younger		Older
B. Interpersonal Relationships	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have to deal with personal harassment	2.22	Low Degree	2.22	Low Degree
2. I have to deal with conflicts with colleagues	2.31	Low Degree	2.27	Low Degree
3. I have to face hostile colleagues towards me	2.36	Low Degree	2.43	Low Degree
4. I have to accept feedback from colleagues	3.53	High Degree	3.20	Moderate Degree
5. I am not appreciated for my work	2.43	Low Degree	2.37	Low Degree
6. I am not given technical assistance	2.21	Low Degree	2.50	Moderate Degree
7. I don't receive respect from my colleagues	1.63	Low Degree	1.92	Low Degree
8. I cannot establish harmonious relationships with my colleagues.	1.64	Low Degree	1.96	Low Degree
9. I solve problems on my own without getting help from my colleagues	2.70	Moderate Degree	2.72	Moderate Degree
10. I have difficulty getting feedback on my work-related issues.	2.24	Low Degree	2.42	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.33	Low Degree	2.40	Low Degree

Table 5 shows the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in terms of interpersonal relationships, categorized by age. Both younger (2.33) and older (2.40) groups reported a "low degree" of stress overall. Item No. 7, "I don't receive respect from my colleagues," received the lowest scores, with younger teachers rating it 1.63 and older teachers 1.92, both interpreted as a "low degree" of stress. On the other hand, Item No. 4, "I have to accept feedback from colleagues," received higher mean scores, with younger teachers rating it 3.53 ("high degree") and older teachers 3.20 ("moderate degree"). The findings indicated that teachers aged 31-50 experienced significantly more stress compared to both younger teachers (20-30) and older teachers (51-60), supporting earlier research by Aftab and Kahtoon (2012) and Azizi Yahaya (2010). The results also align with Sarabia & Collantes (2020), who found that while teachers generally maintained positive relationships with colleagues, social intelligence and professional jealousy could still contribute to stress in the workplace.

Table 6
Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Roles According to Age

Categories		Younger		Older
C. Job Roles	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have many workloads.	3.58	High Degree	3.67	High Degree
2. I have colleagues with conflicting ideas.	2.38	Low Degree	2.51	Moderate Degree
3. I have colleagues who overlap his job roles with mine.	2.14	Low Degree	2.14	Low Degree
4. I have unclear job descriptions.	2.10	Low Degree	2.15	Low Degree
5. I have poor interpersonal relationships	1.86	Low Degree	2.02	Low Degree
6. I lack proper orientation about my job	1.72	Low Degree	2.01	Low Degree
7. I have my limitations when it comes to my duties and responsibilities.	2.93	Moderate Degree	2.68	Moderate Degree
8. I cannot align my job rules with my future promotion.	2.14	Low Degree	2.23	Low Degree
9. I have broad (unclear) objectives and goals.	2.07	Low Degree	2.23	Low Degree
10. I have no direction in my career path.	1.74	Low Degree	2.02	Low Degree

Overall Mean	2.27	Low Degree	2.37	Low Degree
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As presented in Table 6, the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job roles according to age showed overall mean scores of 2.27 for the younger group and 2.37 for the older group, both interpreted as "low degree".

Both the younger and older groups reported that Item No. 1 with the highest mean scores of 3.58 and 3.67, which states "I have many workloads," interpreted as "high degree," while Item No. 6 got the lowest mean scores of 1.72 and 2.01, correspondingly, which states "I lack proper orientation about my job" interpreted as "low degree."

This implies that because of their professional role as a teacher, older teachers usually minimize the workload due to their ability to assess their job role (Dawn et al., 2017). Furthermore, older teachers may be more seasoned environmentally adaptable and mature to cope with stress. In addition, young teachers teaching disruptive students may not be comfortable enough since they are most likely inexperienced in their career compared to their older counterparts (Dawn et al., 2017).

Table 7

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Demands According to Highest Educational Attainment

Categories	Mea n	Lower Interpretation	Mea n	Higher Interpretation
A. Job Demands				
<i>As a teacher, I have</i>				
1. too many ancillary tasks.	3.97	High Degree	4.31	High Degree
2. time pressured with deadlines like LIS, student profile, and parents' directory.	4.08	High Degree	4.32	High Degree
3. overload teaching schedules	3.72	High Degree	3.90	High Degree
4. difficulties in classroom management, like dealing with pupil's misbehavior	3.60	High Degree	3.61	High Degree
5. hard time sustaining pupil's motivation to learn	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.52	High Degree
6. insufficient time in making my Daily Lesson Plan, Daily Lesson Log, and Instructional Materials	3.85	High Degree	3.96	High Degree
7. a big number of pupils to handle in my class	3.37	Moderate Degree	3.40	Moderate Degree
8. too many papers to be done for submission.	4.17	High Degree	4.28	High Degree
9. too many things to do and not enough time to do it.	4.17	High Degree	4.43	High Degree
10. to follow-up SF10, PSA Birth Certificate of students who transferred in.	3.43	Moderate Degree	3.57	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.78	High Degree	3.93	High Degree

Table 7 shows the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job demands according to highest educational attainment. Both the lower group (3.78) and the higher group (3.93) reported a "high degree" of stress overall. In the lower group, Items No. 8 and 9, which state "too many papers to be done for submission" and "too many things to do and not enough time to do it," received the highest mean score of 4.17, while the higher group rated Item No. 9 with a mean score of 4.43. This suggests that both groups experienced similar stressors, particularly related to insufficient time to complete tasks. However, both groups were less affected by the issue of too much paperwork. These findings align with Agai-Demjaha et al. (2017), who found that teachers with higher education levels generally associated their workplace with higher stress. Additionally, the study revealed that teachers with 11-15 years of teaching experience reported more stress than other experience groups, which contrasts with Siong's (2012) study that found no significant difference between stress levels and teaching experience.

Table 8

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Interpersonal Relationships According to Highest Educational Attainment

Categories	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
B. Interpersonal Relationships				
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have to deal with personal harassment	2.21	Low Degree	2.22	Low Degree
2. I have to deal with conflicts with colleagues	2.24	Low Degree	2.38	Low Degree

3. I have to face hostile colleagues towards me	2.32	Low Degree	2.52	Moderate Degree
4. I have to accept feedback from colleagues	3.33	Moderate Degree	3.44	Moderate Degree
5. I am not appreciated for my work	2.23	Low Degree	2.70	Moderate Degree
6. I am not given technical assistance	2.21	Low Degree	2.59	Moderate Degree
7. I don't receive respect from my colleagues	1.71	Low Degree	1.86	Low Degree
8. I cannot establish harmonious relationships with my colleagues.	1.75	Low Degree	1.86	Low Degree
9. I solve problems on my own without getting help from my colleagues	2.68	Moderate Degree	2.77	Moderate Degree
10. I have difficulty getting feedback on my work-related issues.	2.29	Low Degree	2.41	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.30	Low Degree	2.48	Low Degree

Table 8 shows that both the lower and higher educational attainment groups perceived the degree of work-related stressors among public elementary school teachers as a "low degree," with overall means of 2.30 and 2.48, respectively. Both groups rated Items No. 7 ("I don't receive respect from my colleagues") and No. 8 ("I cannot establish harmonious relationships with my colleagues") with the lowest mean score of 1.86, interpreted as "low degree" for the higher group, while the lower group rated Item No. 7 with a mean of 1.71. In contrast, Item 4 ("I have to accept feedback from colleagues") received the highest mean scores of 3.33 and 3.44, interpreted as a "moderate degree." These findings suggest that interpersonal relationships among teachers are generally harmonious, with conflicts between colleagues not serving as a significant source of stress. This aligns with Sarabia & Collantes (2020), who found that elementary school teachers did not experience significant stress in dealing with their co-workers, likely due to good camaraderie and respectful relationships in the workplace.

Table 9
Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Roles According to Highest Educational Attainment

Categories	Mea n	Lower Interpretation	Mea n	Higher Interpretation
C. Job Roles				
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have many workloads.	3.54	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
2. I have colleagues with conflicting ideas.	2.38	Low Degree	2.54	Moderate Degree
3. I have colleagues who overlap his job roles with mine.	2.05	Low Degree	2.29	Low Degree
4. I have unclear job descriptions.	1.99	Low Degree	2.35	Low Degree
5. I have poor interpersonal relationships	1.92	Low Degree	1.98	Low Degree
6. I lack proper orientation about my job	1.82	Low Degree	1.94	Low Degree
7. I have my limitations when it comes to my duties and responsibilities.	2.75	Moderate Degree	2.91	Moderate Degree
8. I cannot align my job roles with my future promotion.	2.09	Low Degree	2.35	Low Degree
9. I have broad (unclear) objectives and goals.	2.09	Low Degree	2.25	Low Degree
10. I have no direction in my career path.	1.83	Low Degree	1.95	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.25	Low Degree	2.43	Low Degree

Table 9 presents the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job roles according to their highest educational attainment. The overall mean scores are 2.25 for the lower group and 2.43 for the higher group, both interpreted as a "low degree." Both groups rated Item No. 1 ("I have many workloads") with the highest mean scores of 3.54 and 3.77, indicating a "high degree," while Item No. 6 ("I lack proper orientation about my job") received the lowest mean scores of 1.82 and 1.94, interpreted as "low degree." These findings suggest that both groups of teacher-respondents were not significantly stressed regarding their workplace roles. One possible reason is that many teachers view their profession as a source of joy, fulfillment, and achievement. This aligns with the research of Sarabia & Collantes (2020), which found a "low degree" of work-related stress among teachers in selected schools in the Philippines, with a computed pooled mean of 2.49.

Table 10

Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Demands According to Plantilla Position

Categories	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
A. Job Demands				
<i>As a teacher, I have</i>				
1. too many ancillary tasks.	4.04	High Degree	4.26	High Degree
2. time pressured with deadlines like LIS, student profile, and parents' directory.	4.16	High Degree	4.19	High Degree
3. overload teaching schedules	3.78	High Degree	3.82	High Degree
4. difficulties in classroom management, like dealing with pupil's misbehavior	3.54	High Degree	3.82	High Degree
5. hard time sustaining pupil's motivation to learn	3.43	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
6. insufficient time in making my Daily Lesson Plan, Daily Lesson Log, and Instructional Materials	3.87	High Degree	3.97	High Degree
7. a big number of pupils to handle in my class	3.36	Moderate Degree	3.45	Moderate Degree
8. too many papers to be done for submission.	4.17	High Degree	4.34	High Degree
9. too many things to do and not enough time to do it.	4.22	High Degree	4.44	High Degree
10. to follow-up SF10, PSA Birth Certificate of students who transferred in.	3.46	Moderate Degree	3.55	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.80	High Degree	3.95	High Degree

Table 10 presents the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in the area of job demands according to plantilla position. The overall mean scores are 3.80 for the lower group and 3.95 for the higher group, both interpreted as "high degree." Both groups rated Item No. 9 ("too many things to do and not enough time to do it") with the highest mean scores of 4.22 and 4.44, indicating a "high degree." They also agreed that Item No. 7 ("a big number of pupils to handle under my class") had the lowest mean scores of 3.36 and 3.45, interpreted as "moderate degree." This suggests that while teachers face challenges with heavy workloads, the number of pupils in their classes is less of a concern. The workload is particularly demanding due to numerous tasks with strict deadlines. This finding is supported by Orlanda-Ventayen & Ventayen's (2021) study, which found high levels of anxiety and depression among teachers in the Philippines, particularly those in lower educational levels such as kindergarten, elementary, and high school.

Table 11
Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Interpersonal Relationships According to Plantilla Position

Categories	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
B. Interpersonal Relationships				
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have to deal with personal harassment	2.20	Low Degree	2.27	Low Degree
2. I have to deal with conflicts with colleagues	2.27	Low Degree	2.37	Low Degree
3. I have to face hostile colleagues towards me	2.37	Low Degree	2.47	Low Degree
4. I have to accept feedback from colleagues	3.32	Moderate Degree	3.53	High Degree
5. I am not appreciated for my work	2.36	Low Degree	2.53	Moderate Degree
6. I am not given technical assistance	2.30	Low Degree	2.55	Moderate Degree
7. I don't receive respect from my colleagues	1.75	Low Degree	1.84	Low Degree
8. I cannot establish harmonious relationships with my colleagues.	1.78	Low Degree	1.81	Low Degree
9. I solve problems on my own without getting help from my colleagues	2.70	Moderate Degree	2.76	Moderate Degree
10. I have difficulty getting feedback on my work-related issues.	2.31	Low Degree	2.39	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.34	Low Degree	2.45	Low Degree

Table 11 presents the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in interpersonal relationships according to plantilla position. The overall mean scores are 2.34 for the lower group and 2.45 for the

higher group, both interpreted as "low degree." Item No. 4 ("I have to accept feedback from colleagues") registered the highest mean scores of 3.32 (moderate degree) and 3.53 (high degree) for the lower and higher groups, respectively. In contrast, Item No. 7 ("I don't receive respect from my colleagues") had the lowest mean score of 1.75 (low degree) for the lower group, while the higher group rated Item No. 8 ("I cannot establish a harmonious relationship with my colleagues") with the lowest mean score of 1.81 (low degree). These results suggest that, although interpersonal relationships were generally not a significant source of stress, some teachers felt a lack of support, particularly in terms of technical assistance from management or experienced personal harassment and conflict with colleagues, albeit to a low degree. This finding aligns with Sarabia & Collantes (2020), who found that the role, support, and relationships with co-workers in Philippine schools contributed to low stress among teachers.

Table 12
Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Roles According to Plantilla Position

Categories	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Roles				
<i>As a teacher,</i>				
1. I have many workloads.	3.55	High Degree	3.90	High Degree
2. I have colleagues with conflicting ideas.	2.39	Low Degree	2.65	Moderate Degree
3. I have colleagues who overlap his job roles with mine.	2.15	Low Degree	2.08	Low Degree
4. I have unclear job descriptions.	2.09	Low Degree	2.24	Low Degree
5. I have poor interpersonal relationships	1.93	Low Degree	1.98	Low Degree
6. I lack proper orientation about my job	1.83	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
7. I have my limitations when it comes to my duties and responsibilities.	2.76	Moderate Degree	2.98	Moderate Degree
8. I cannot align my job rules with my future promotion.	2.13	Low Degree	2.39	Low Degree
9. I have broad (unclear) objectives and goals.	2.12	Low Degree	2.26	Low Degree
10. I have no direction in my career path.	1.87	Low Degree	1.89	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.28	Low Degree	2.44	Low Degree

Table 12 depicts the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in job roles according to plantilla position. Both the lower and higher groups were interpreted as experiencing a "low degree" of stress, with overall mean scores of 2.28 and 2.44, respectively. Item No. 1 ("I have many workloads") received the highest mean scores of 3.55 and 3.90, indicating that heavy workloads contributed to their "high degree" of stress. In contrast, the lower group rated Item No. 6 ("I lack proper orientation about my job") with the lowest mean score of 1.83, while the higher group rated Item No. 10 ("I have no direction in my career path") with a mean score of 1.89, both interpreted as "low degree." The results indicate that teachers feel highly stressed by heavy workloads, but the lack of job orientation and career direction also negatively impacts them. These challenges arise from the conflict between their work demands, such as paperwork, and the absence of decision-making power, as they are often directed to implement decisions without having their voices heard. Brown (2018) noted that poor task management, especially with paperwork and additional responsibilities, can be a significant stressor for teachers.

Table 13
Difference in the Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Demands When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	148	144.13	9971.500	0.810		Not Significant
	Older	137	141.78				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	182	136.33	8159.000	0.069	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	103	154.79				
Plantilla Position	Lower	223	138.74	5964.000	0.098		Not Significant
	Higher	62	158.31				

Table 13 indicates that there is no significant difference in the degree of work-related stressors among public elementary school teachers in the area of job demands when grouped by age, highest educational attainment, and

plantilla position. All computed p-values, ranging from 0.069 to 0.8100, were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference based on these variables. This suggests that regardless of their demographic characteristics, teachers' work-related stressors do not vary significantly across different groups. The results imply that teachers, irrespective of age, education, or position, possess high coping capabilities, driven by their commitment to their profession and desire to maintain their jobs. This finding contrasts with the study by Marinaccio et al. (2018), which found a significant interaction between educational level and work-related stress, indicating that teachers with higher education perceived more job demands and role ambiguity.

Table 14

Difference in the Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Area Interpersonal Relationships When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	148	139.61	9636.500	0.470		Not Significant
	Older	137	146.66				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	182	135.04	7924.500	0.030	0.05	Significant
	Higher	103	157.06				
Plantilla Position	Lower	223	139.58	6151.000	0.184		Not Significant
	Higher	62	155.29				

Table 14 reveals a significant difference in the degree of work-related stressors among public elementary school teachers in the area of interpersonal relationships, specifically when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The Mann-Whitney U-Test yielded a value of 7924.500 with a p-value of 0.030, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the teachers' experience of work-related stress in interpersonal relationships varies with their educational background. Teachers with higher levels of education may be better equipped with advanced problem-solving skills, coping strategies, and confidence when managing workplace relationships, whereas teachers with lower educational levels might face more difficulties in communication and collaboration, leading to higher stress. As a result, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in stress based on educational attainment was rejected. However, no significant differences were found when grouping by age and plantilla position, as the p-values for these comparisons were above 0.05. This means that teachers' interpersonal stress levels do not significantly differ by age or plantilla position. These findings align with Marinaccio et al. (2018), who suggested that a higher educational level enhances workplace relationships. Teachers in lower educational attainment groups, often newer to the profession, may experience higher interpersonal stress due to challenges in asserting themselves and the pressures of promotion and job security.

Table 15

Difference in the Degree of Work-Related Stressors of Public Elementary School Teachers in Job Roles When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	148	138.74	9508.000	0.364		Not Significant
	Older	137	147.60				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	182	134.88	7895.500	0.027	0.05	Significant
	Higher	103	157.34				
Plantilla Position	Lower	223	138.56	5922.000	0.084		Not Significant
	Higher	62	158.98				

Table 15 presents the difference in the degree of work-related stressors of public elementary school teachers in job roles, grouped by age, highest educational attainment, and plantilla position. The Mann-Whitney U-Test revealed no significant differences when grouped by age (9508.000, p = 0.364) and plantilla position (5922.000, p = 0.084), as the p-values were above the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in work-related stressors based on age and plantilla position was accepted. However, when grouped by highest educational attainment, the Mann-Whitney U-Test result (7895.500, p = 0.027) was below the 0.05 significance

threshold, indicating a significant difference. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in stress levels based on educational attainment was rejected. The findings suggest that educational level is significantly associated with work-related stressors, with lower educational levels linked to higher stress. This aligns with studies from Kosovo, Nepal, European countries, and Malaysia (Othman et al., 2019), suggesting that teachers with lower education may struggle more with the complexities of the teaching role, resulting in higher stress levels.

Conclusions:

Most teacher-respondents were younger, with lower educational attainment, and belonged to the lower plantilla position group. The degree of work-related stressors was "high" in job demands but "low" in interpersonal relationships and job roles. Both younger and older respondents rated their stress in job demands as "high" while assessing interpersonal relationships and job roles as "low." Similarly, respondents from both lower and higher educational attainment groups rated job demands as "high" and interpersonal relationships and job roles as "low." Regarding plantilla position, both groups rated job demands as "high" while interpersonal relationships and job roles were rated "low." No significant differences were found in job demands when compared by age, educational attainment, or plantilla position. However, significant differences were observed in interpersonal relationships when grouped by educational attainment. The findings suggest that, while work-related stress in job demands is consistently high across groups, stress from interpersonal relationships and job roles is generally low, with higher groups experiencing slightly more stress. Despite these variations, no substantial differences in responses were found across demographic groups regarding job demands, though responses differed more significantly in interpersonal relationships and job roles when grouped by educational attainment. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that schools foster an environment of open communication and collaboration between school officials and teachers. School authorities should create a work-life balance by providing a conducive teaching environment and assigning non-teaching staff to handle administrative tasks. Reducing manual paperwork through automated platforms and redefining teachers' job descriptions to focus on primary teaching duties is essential. Additionally, establishing a "buddy system" among teachers and encouraging regular discussions with school heads can improve relationships. Teachers should be offered technical assistance and participate in seminars on stress management. Finally, a psycho-social wellness plan should be developed to balance job demands, enhance interpersonal relationships, and clearly define job roles with provisions for recognition and incentives.

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